

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from Svælget 2, a wreck found at the mouth of Copenhagen Harbour, Denmark.

Aoife Daly

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Samples from a shipwreck, found during archaeological survey and excavation in Copenhagen Harbour, were submitted to the International Dendrochronology Research Laboratory Dendro.dk, for dendrochronological analysis. The ship has been given the name Svælget 2 and it is identified as a ship of 'Bremen Type' or a Cog. Samples from the ship structure and from barrels have been analysed. The results of the analysis of these samples are described in this report.

Svælget 2 ship timbers

Twenty-eight of the samples analysed are timbers from the ship structure. These include samples from compass timbers (frames, keel, keelson) and from planking (hull planks, presumed fore- and stern castle planks). Two samples were only examined to determine wood genus, as they contained too few tree rings for a dendrochronological analysis. These are listed in the catalogue at the end of this report.

Of the 26 timbers from the ship that were analysed dendrochronologically, two are pine (*Pinus* sp.), while the remaining are all oak (*Quercus* sp.). Fifteen samples from the ship structure could be dated.

The non-plank timbers

Thirteen timbers are from internal elements. Eight of these are from futtocks, and there are samples from the keel, the keelson, a frame element, a beam and a rubbing strake.

Seven of the samples from the internal timbers could not be dated, and these all contain relatively few tree rings (see catalogue).

Six of the internal timbers are dated. Based on the provenance of these dated timbers (see below) two groups are identified:

The blue group (Fig. 1, Table 1)

Three frames, x1684, x180 and x367, are assigned to the blue group. One of these, x367, has sapwood preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling of the tree that this frame element was made from can be placed in the period AD 1400-1407. The other two frames in this blue group have *termini post quem* dating estimates after AD 1329 and after AD 1395 respectively.

The orange group

Three of the dated internal timbers are placed in the orange group. These are futtocks x354 and x67 and keelson x63. All three samples in the orange group have sapwood preserved, and one, the keelson, might have bark edge.

The futtocks are from trees felled in AD 1399-1414 and AD 1402-1420, respectively. The keelson is from a tree that might have been felled in AD 1400-1401.

Fig. 1. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. The chronological position of the dated samples.

The planks

Thirteen samples are from planks from the ship. Five are from hull planks, two are ceiling planks and four are from the cladding of presumed fore- and stern castles. Two pine samples are from a probable deck plank and the topmost starboard hull plank, possibly a sort of wash strake.

Four plank samples, three oak and one pine, could not be dated (see catalogue).

These are from the two ceiling planks, from one hull plank and the probable pine deck plank, and they all contain relatively few tree-rings.

Nine plank samples are dated.

The pale orange group

Three of these, x491, x60 & x62 (all oak), can be grouped together, in terms of their provenance (see below and highlighted with pale orange in fig. 1 and Table 1). These three are hull planks, and none of them have sapwood preserved. The tree-ring curves for samples x60 and x62 are so similar, it indicates that these two planks might have been fashioned from the same tree. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling of this tree can be placed at after AD 1359 (see fig. 1). The third plank in this group, x491, is from a tree felled after AD 1353.

The pale blue group

A fourth hull plank, x296, has a different provenance than the three planks described above. It has sapwood preserved. It is from a tree felled in the period AD 1396-1410.

An oak sample from the presumed stern castle, x293, also has sapwood preserved. It is from a tree felled in the period c. AD 1396-1410.

Three plank samples, x407, x209 & x203, all oak, are from the wall of the ship's presumed forecastle. One, x407, has only heartwood preserved, and it is from a tree felled after AD 1382. The other two have sapwood preserved. They are from trees felled in AD 1393-1401 and AD 1396-1407 respectively.

Lastly, the pine plank is dated (shown with brown shading in fig. 1). Its outermost measured ring was formed in AD 1404 and an incomplete ring is observed outermost on the sample. Bark edge was not observed. This board is from a tree felled after AD 1405.

Svælget 2 onboard artefacts

Possibly representing the ship's provisions, a single sample from a wood piece interpreted as firewood was analysed. Additionally, samples from 16 barrel staves, representing either cargo or provisions, were analysed. Of these 17 samples, 16 are dated.

The firewood

The oak sample from the firewood contains just 39 tree rings, including 10 sapwood rings and probable bark edge. It was possible to date this piece (shown in yellow in fig. 1). It is from a tree that was probably felled in AD 1401-02.

The barrel staves

Fifteen of the 16 samples from the barrel staves are dated. Their chronological placement is shown in fig. 1, highlighted with dark blue. Five of the staves have sapwood, and the dating results for these suggest a mixed chronological collection. Sample x864 is from a tree felled in the period AD 1380-94. Sample x1045 is from a tree felled in AD 1394-95. Sample from stave x1233 is from AD 1397-1408. Stave x328 is from a tree felled in AD 1398-1405, and finally, the sample from stave x1368 is from a tree probably felled in 1406-07 (see fig. 1).

	Z3110029 x0060	Z3110089 x491	Z3110109 x67	Z3110279 x63	Z3110219 x354	Z3110159 x203	Z311017a x209	Z311016a x407	Z3110289 x293	Z3110039 x0296	Z311001a x1684	Z311024a x367	Z3110099 x180	Z311041a x619	Z311036a x1045	Z311032a x864	Z311014a x1101	Z311034a x1087	Z311031a x1233	Z311042a x750	Z311038a x1045	Z311029a x1368	Z311040a x204	Z311043a x1043	Z311033a x427	Z311044a x1095	Z311039a x328	Z311035a x1328	Z3110049 x0299	Z3110269 x1497	
M002		10.44	3.02	1.55	2.97	0.29									0.47					0.71	0.58	0.99	1.26						0.18		
	Z3110029 x0060		10.44*	3.02	1.55	2.97	0.29								0.47					0.71	0.58	0.99	1.26						0.18		
	Z311030a x62	10.44*	0.6						1.09				1.96		0.07					0.48	0.99	1.26	2.05	1.37		0.83	0.06				
	Z3110089 x491	3.02	0.6*		1.29	2.52	1.75	0.29	0.22				0.51		0.38				1	0.26	1.6	0.18	1.1	0.24	0.61	1			1.43		
	Z3110109 x67				4.87	1.91	2.64	1.86	0.66	0.24			2.28	0.19	1.38					1.21	1.57	0.33	2.77	0.32	2.79	3.35	3.45	3.39		1.02	2.45
	Z3110279 x63	1.55		1.29	4.87*	3.22	0.65	2.03	0.95	0.25			4.19	2.01	0.95	0.87	0.87			1.21	1.19	1.21	1.61	2.63	0.93	0.36	2.73	0.03	0.27	0.86	
	Z3110219 x354	2.97		2.52	1.91	3.22*	0.69	0.93					0.73	1.41	0.12	1.43	0.23			0.08	0.72	0.62	1.59	1.69	1.82	0.46	0.83	0.8	0.31	0.21	1.85
	Z3110159 x203			2.64	0.65	0.69*	2.17	1.41	3.8	0.06	1.26	2.76	0.51	2.68	2.64	1.87	2.11	1.18	0.54	2.42	2.68	1.04	2.64	1.31	2.66	2.13	0.26	1.2	0.36		
	Z311017a x209	0.29		1.75	1.86	2.03	0.93	2.17*	5.53	2.97	0.89	1.43	1.93	1.79	3.87	3.7	3.69	2.08	3.52	2.78	4.36	2.46	2.92	2.96	1.92	2.43	0.8	3.14	1.6	-	0.22
	Z311016a x407		1.09	0.29	0.66	0.95	1.41	5.53*	4.65	2.15	0.32	1.83	0.26	2.32	1.82	2.48	1.34	1.91	1.15	3.16	0.95	0.23	0.6	1.24	1.52	3.3	0.65	0.08			
	Z3110289 x293				0.25	3.8	2.97	4.65*	3.74	2.46	1.86	0.28	0.9	1.65	1.97	2.69	0.43			2.2	1.55					1.53	0.65	2.3			
	Z3110039 x0296			0.22	0.24	0.06	0.89	2.15	3.74*	1.68	0.73	1.33	1.77	1.2	2.46	1.33	0.47	1.78	4.12	3.91					1.55	2.42	0.64	2.78	0.55	0.82	
	Z311001a x1684				1.26	1.43	0.32	2.46	1.68*	1.64	2.94	3.82	2.8	3.47	1.84	3.33	3.27	0.88	1.06	1.18	0.85	1.26	2.36	2.14	1.49	0.1					
	Z311024a x367	1.96		2.28	4.19	0.73	2.76	1.93	1.83	1.86	0.73	1.64*	1.24	3.87	2.39	3.9	1.97	3.18	2.86	2.79	2.63	1.5	3.12	2.45	1.77	2	1.34	3.25	1.17	0.61	
	Z3110099 x180	0	0.51	0.19	2.01	1.41	0.51	1.79	0.26	0.28	1.33	2.94	1.24*	6.6	4.27	5.34	3.2	3.8	3.95	4.17	2.86	4.01	3.76	3.01	3.67	2.72	0.97	2.77	-	1.4	
	Z311041a x619			1.38	0.95	0.12	2.68	3.87	2.32	0.9	1.77	3.82	3.87	6.6*	5.46	5.3	4.48	4.59	3.53	3.96	2.59	3.2	4.67	2.83	3.01	2.1	2.58	2.88	1.35		
	Z311036a x1045	0.47		0.38	0.87	1.43	2.64	3.7	1.82	1.65	1.2	2.8	2.39	4.27	5.46*	4.07	3.69	3.34	3.45	1.98	3.14	3.41	2.58	3.65	3.37	0.65		3.06			
	Z311032a x864		0.07	2.12	0.87	0.23	1.87	3.69	2.48	1.97	2.46	3.47	3.9	5.34	5.3	4.07*	3.69	4.73	4.34	4.63	4.12	4.22	3.85	3.22	3.54	4.5	1.7	3	-	2.09	
	Z311014a x1101			1			2.11	2.08	1.34	2.69	1.33	1.84	1.97	3.2	4.48	3.69	3.69*	5.95	4.51	1.3	1.84	0.76		2.4	1.7	2.6	1.83	2.52			
	Z311034a x1087		0.26	1.33	1.21	0.08	1.18	3.52	1.91	0.43	0.47	3.33	3.18	3.8	4.59	3.34	4.73	5.95*	11.94	5.34	5.03	3.68	1.41	2.96	2.82	1.81	3.32	2.14		-	2.61
	Z311031a x1233		1.6	1.57	1.19	0.72	0.54	2.78	1.15	1.78	3.27	2.86	3.95	3.53	3.45	4.34	4.51	11.94*	4.8	4.86	3.76	1.27	2.93	2.73	3.37	4.41	4.11		-	2.43	
	Z311042a x750	0.71	0.48	0.18	0.33	0.62	2.42	4.36	3.16	2.2	4.12	0.88	2.79	4.17	3.96	1.98	4.63	1.3	5.34	4.8*	7.61	3.74	3.08	2.66	4.38	2.97	2.63	2.29	0.16	0.91	
	Z311038a x1045	0.58		1.1	2.77	1.21	1.59	2.68	2.46	1.55	3.91	1.06	2.63	2.86	2.59	3.14	4.12	1.84	5.03	4.86	7.61*	3.88	3.3	1.94	2.84	2.7	1.72	3.38	0.53	1.52	
	Z311029a x1368		0.24	0.32	1.61	1.69	1.04	2.92	0.95			1.18	1.5	4.01	3.2	3.41	4.22	0.76	3.68	3.76	3.74	3.88*	6.04	5.02	4.32	1.66	1.58	2.23	0.27	2.9	
	Z311040a x204	0.99	2.05	0.61	2.79	2.63	1.82	2.64	2.96	0.23		0.85	3.12	3.76	4.67	2.58	3.85		1.41	1.27	3.08	3.3	6.04*	5.22	4.13	2.74	2.5	0.91	0.81	1.12	
	Z311043a x1043	1.26	1.37	1	3.35	0.93	1.31	1.92	0.6			1.26	2.45	3.01	2.83	3.65	3.22	2.4	2.96	2.93	2.66	1.94	5.02	5.22*	3.42	2.72	1.8	1.22	-	3.25	
	Z311033a x427				0.46	2.66	2.43	1.24		1.55	2.36	1.77	3.67	3.01	3.37	3.54	1.7	2.82	2.73	4.38	2.84	4.32	4.13	3.42*	2.22	0.93	2.38	-	1.85		
	Z311044a x1095		0.83	3.45	0.36	0.83	2.13	0.8	1.52	1.53	2.42	2.14	2	2.72	2.1	0.65	4.5	2.6	1.81	3.37	2.97	2.7	1.66	2.74	2.72	2.22*	3.57	0.5	0.52	1.66	
	Z311039a x328		0.06	3.39	2.73	0.8	0.26	3.14	3.3		0.64	1.49	1.34	0.97	2.58		1.7	1.83	3.32	4.41	2.63	1.72	1.58	2.5	1.8	0.93	3.57*	0.08	1.05	1.51	
	Z311035a x1328			1.43	0.03	0.31	1.2	1.6	0.65	0.65	2.78	0.1	3.25	2.77	2.88	3.06	3	2.52	2.14	4.11	2.29	3.38	2.23	0.91	1.22	2.38	0.5	0.08			
	Z3110049 x0299	0.18		1.02	0.27	0.21	0.36	-	0.08	2.3	0.55	1.17	-	1.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.16	0.53	0.27	0.81	-	-	0.52	1.05			
	Z3110269 x1497			2.45	0.86	1.85	-	0.22		-	0.82		0.61	1.4		2.09		2.61	2.43	0.91	1.52	2.9	1.12	3.25	1.85	1.66	1.51	-			

Table 1. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation (t -value) of each dated tree-ring curve from the shipwreck against each other.

07 March 2025

Svælget 2 provenance

The internal correlation (each sample with each other) between the 31 dated tree-ring curves from the Svælget 2 wreck site is shown in table 1. There are small groups of samples that correlate well with each other, but the material as a whole is generally heterogeneous, many of the samples are dating independently. Two main timber sources are identified in this process, and the colours serve to identify these groups.

Three inboard timbers and three planks from the ship are assigned the orange and pale orange groups respectively, and an average of these six is made, Z311M002, representing five trees. This average is 154 year long and covers the period AD 1248-1401. The correlations between the orange average and diverse tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe are shown in table 2. The orange group average is matching strongest with regional master chronologies from the Low Countries. But the highest correlation is with a site chronology from Lower Saxony. The trees that belong in the orange group might come from diverse sources within this larger region.

Filename	start year-end year	Z311M002 NL Svælget 2 AD1248- AD1401	site name
Master chronologies			
TWWFMD01	AD1216-AD1660	6.93	NL Twente/Westfalen 51 trees (Dominguez Delmas unpubl)
nlmidden	AD1023-AD1666	6.40	Mid Netherlands (Jansma 1995)
nlzuidmm	AD427-AD1752	5.67	South Netherlands (Jansma 1995)
DM200004	30BC-AD1960	5.30	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
DM700001	AD631-AD1950	5.23	Southern Germany (Huber + Becker?)
DM200006	AD914-AD1873	4.90	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
arden4	AD1146-AD1991	4.74	Arden4 (Hoffsummer via Haneca pers comm)
WD400std	AD400-AD1975	4.63	SW Germany (Hollstein 1980)
meuse2	AD672-AD1989	4.56	Meuse (Tegel pers comm)
FRnordest1	AD641-AD1988	4.50	France NE (Tegel pers comm)
Site chronologies			
G311YZ02	AD1324-AD1575	7.66	Hann.Münden 35 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3416Z01	AD1284-AD1489	5.44	Braunschweig 8 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
NL225541	AD1213-AD1641	5.24	Zutphen Binnenstad (Van Daalen pers comm)
G311RZ01	AD1320-AD1548	4.76	Helmarshausen 12 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from ships			
Z334M003	AD1123-AD1356	5.49	Varberg 3 14 timbers (Daly 2025)

Table 2. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation between the average of the Low Countries group (Z311M002) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Three frames and five planks from the ship form the blue/pale-blue group. Again, this group is heterogeneous, but correlations of the individual samples indicate a similar region of origin, so these eight timbers are averaged to Z311M001. This average is 300 year long, and it covers the period AD 1100-1399. It is correlating with a wide range of northern European datasets, highest with a chronology for Gdansk in current-day Poland (table 3). The trees of this group grew in the region around the mouth of the Vistula River. The group average is also showing very significant correlations with a range of datasets for ship planks, barrels and various other planks and boards, all dating to late 14th and early 15th centuries. These datasets have been shown, through dendrochronology, to represent trees from the region around the mouth of the Vistula River, and these results remind us of the

extensive exploitation of planking, boards and staves from this region, that were traded to western Europe (Daly 2011a).

Filename	start year-end year	Z311M001 PL ship AD1100- AD1399	site name
Master chronologies			
PM670108	AD725-AD1985	10.70	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
P671001m	AD980-AD1347	9.29	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
2021BLT2	AD1186-AD1618	9.06	2021 Baltic2 449 trees (Daly & Tyers 2022)
POL WIEL	AD1197-AD1606	8.83	West Central Poland Wielkopolska (M Krapiec pers comm)
2021BLT1	AD1143-AD1626	7.68	2021 Baltic1 552 trees (Daly & Tyers 2022)
Site chronologies			
PUCKM002	AD1134-AD1329	10.94	Puck 3 timbers (Wazny pers comm)
PP147M01	AD1151-AD1363	8.45	PL Jeziernik 10 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP111M01	AD1136-AD1399	8.24	PL Gdansk St Nikolaus 11 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP123M01	AD1049-AD1311	8.18	PL Elblag 43 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP116M01	AD1174-AD1358	7.92	PL Gdansk Kobziarz 11 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP125M01	AD917-AD1400	7.90	PL Elblag 150 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP103M01	AD1136-AD1335	7.79	PL Gdansk Ratusz 10 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP124M01	AD982-AD1356	7.50	PL Elblag 120 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP102M02	AD1085-AD1361	7.47	PL Gdansk 19 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP105M01	AD1140-AD1374	7.22	PL Gdansk Grodzka 3 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from ships			
CLS2000	AD1110-AD1393	10.92	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire 11 boat planks (Tyers pers comm)
02071M01	AD1126-AD1414	10.28	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
Z076m003 all	AD1097-AD1393	9.21	Skjernøysund all 19 timbers (Daly 2011b, 2019a)
Z223M001	AD1126-AD1411	8.41	Peenemündung Fp1105 planks 4 timbers (Daly 2019b)
Z0051Mall	AD1063-AD1373	8.24	Bole all 48 timbers (Daly & Nymoen in prep)
0045M002	AD1109-AD1370	7.40	Vejby ship 18 timbers (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
Chronologies from barrels			
StCrux27	AD1144-AD1388	9.59	York St Crux Church decorative bosses (Tyers pers comm)
2129M001	AD1125-AD1399	9.45	Copenhagen N. Hemmingsensg. barrel 3 timbers (Daly 2000, 2007)
os160 t7	AD1138-AD1382	9.17	York Vicars Choral Large Table 7 boards (Tyers pers comm)
GNT.PPS.M3	AD1247-AD1362	8.18	Peperstraat Gent barrel 5 timbers (Haneca pers comm)
0056M001	AD1174-AD1335	7.55	Aberdeen barrel (Crone pers comm)
H038M005	AD1182-AD1414	7.54	Aalborg Algade mm group 5 barrel staves 6 timbers (Daly 2022)
Chronologies from (Baltic) boards			
HMC T165	AD1078-AD1369	11.66	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
P0011009	AD1103-AD1403	8.53	Wainscot cargo Copper Ship (Wazny pers comm)
wm2029a14	AD1211-AD1310	7.30	Gl. Åby Kirkegård Århus barrel (Sønderby pers comm)
GB00M001	AD1165-AD1386	7.28	London ABB87 Door (Tyers pers comm)
NWCOLLG2	AD1086-AD1357	7.22	New College Oxford door Baltic 4 timbers (Worthington & Miles 2006)

Table 3. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation between the average of the Vistula ship timbers group (Z311M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

The tree-ring curves from the 15 dated barrel stave samples are averaged to a mean curve, Z311M003. This average is 214 years long and covers the period AD 1193-1406. This average is correlating strongly with the Gdansk master chronology, and it also correlates very strongly with a range of site chronologies from around the gulf of Gdansk (table 4). The barrel stave average also correlates with datasets for other 14th century barrels and ships from western Europe. The barrel staves are made from trees that also grew in the region around the mouth of the Vistula River. The blue/pale-blue group of timbers from the ship cross-matches with the dark-blue barrel stave group with a *t*-value of 6.77. All in all, the evidence suggests that the ‘Vistula’ ship timbers and the ‘Vistula’ barrel staves are from slightly different areas within the same region.

Filename	start year-end year	Z311M003 PL staves AD1193- AD1406	site name
Master chronologies			
PM670108	AD725-AD1985	16.51	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
Site chronologies			
P719M001	AD1309-AD1551	13.64	Tolkicko 7 timbers (Wazny pers comm)
PP111M01	AD1136-AD1399	12.53	PL Gdansk St Nikolaus 11 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P676001m	AD1084-AD1393	12.51	Poland Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
PUCKM002	AD1134-AD1329	12.24	Puck 3 timbers (Wazny pers comm)
P671001m	AD980-AD1347	11.98	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
0680001S	AD1121-AD1398	11.04	Gdansk St Nikolaus (Wazny pers comm)
PP106M01	AD1110-AD1399	10.91	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
0686003s	AD1140-AD1390	10.75	Poland Przermark (Wazny pers comm)
PP124M01	AD982-AD1356	10.74	PL Elblag 120 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP118M01	AD1112-AD1399	10.21	PL Gdansk various 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
0704002s	AD1151-AD1363	9.87	Poland Jeziernik (Wazny pers comm)
PP114M01	AD1152-AD1447	9.69	PL Gdansk Wole Rogi 18 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP142M01	AD1129-AD1390	9.66	PL Przermark Glocken 19 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from ships			
0045M002	AD1109-AD1370	11.82	Vejby ship 18 timbers (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
00121M01	AD1155-AD1353	10.78	Lille Kregme 8 timbers (Erikson 1992)
Z005M002	AD1177-AD1356	9.93	Bølevraget Norge four beams 4 timbers (Daly & Nymoen 2008)
Chronologies from barrels			
H038M005	AD1182-AD1414	13.76	Aalborg Algade group 5 barrel staves 6 timbers (Daly 2022)
Z121barrels 4&5	AD1105-AD1343	11.73	Thomas B Triges latrine barrels 4&5. 11 timbers (Daly 2015)
0056M001	AD1174-AD1335	11.46	Aberdeen barrel (Crone pers comm)
wm2029a14	AD1211-AD1310	10.30	Gl. Åby Kirkegård Århus barrel (Sønderby pers comm)
w522b10019	AD1264-AD1402	9.73	Boller Slot barrel (Christensen pers comm)
B0111m01	AD1201-AD1417	9.64	Kompagnistræde Næstved polish barrel 2 timbers (Daly 2007)
GNT.PPS.M3	AD1247-AD1362	8.94	Peperstraat Gent barrel 5 timbers (Haneca pers comm)

Table 4. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation between the average of the barrel staves (dark blue group) (Z311M003) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

The pine plank is dating with master chronologies for pine from current-day Poland (table 5). The two highest matching chronologies are for the region south of the Gulf of Gdansk, and the pine that was used for this plank probably grew in the Lower Vistula region.

Filename	start year-end year	Z3110049 x0299 Pine AD1339- AD1404	site name
Master chronologies			
P810001M	AD1186-AD1397	6.50	Tarnowo Paluckie pine (Wazny pers comm)
pol_kuja	AD1168-AD2000	6.36	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
pol_skan	AD1168-AD1994	5.62	Poland north central pine (Zielski 1997)
Site chronologies			
zp7mkpc1	AD1137-AD1511	3.85	Vilnius Castle 10 timbers pine (Puckiene pers comm)

Table 5. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from the pine plank (Z3110049) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filename	start year-end year	Z3110269 x1497 firewood AD1363- AD1401	site name
Master chronologies oak			
OsloGr1	AD1317-AD1601	5.28	Oslo ships Group 1 70 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SM000005	AD1274-AD1974	4.5	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
Site chronologies			
LS201M01	AD1347-AD1453	6.17	Southwest Sweden 4 timbers (Lund Uni revised Daly 2007)
81272M01	AD935-AD1541	5.69	Aalborg Boulevarden (Daly 2001)
B087M001	AD1353-AD1566	4.8	Oluf I Jensens gård Køge 3 timbers (Daly 2023a)
8102M002	AD1386-AD1457	4.52	Bindeslev K. Hjørring 4 timbers (Daly 1998)
Chronologies from ships			
Z160M008 all	AD1317-AD1557	5.22	Bispevika 8 ship Oslo all 22 timbers (Daly 2023b)
H051M002	AD1145-AD1587	5.04	Mølleplads Aalborg 20 timbers (Daly in prep)
Z280M001	AD1362-AD1564	4.68	Femern 'Delmenhorst' VIR2929 3 timbers (Daly 2020)
Master chronologies pine			
gaepin01	AD1212-AD1883	7.24	Gaestrikland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD1127-AD1671	5.11	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_UP1	AD1031-AD1638	4.89	Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
dalpinus	AD931-AD1888	4.87	Dalarna (Eggertsson pers comm)
30530010	AD1343-AD1669	4.75	Skeppsholmen Stockholm 36 series (Eggertsson pers comm)

Table 6. Svælget 2, Copenhagen Harbour. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from the firewood (Z3110269) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Finally, the piece of firewood is dating against a wide range of oak datasets for southern Scandinavia (table 6). It is also showing significant correlation with pine master chronologies. It is not possible to be more specific about the provenance of this single, relatively short tree-ring series.

Interpretation

To sum up, the dendrochronological analysis of Svælget 2 indicates that the trees for the building of the ship were felled around AD 1400-1401 (indicated with a pink vertical line in fig. 1). This is interpreted through examination of the felling date estimates for all samples, many of which fall very close to the probable felling date for x63, with probable bark edge preserved, at AD 1400-1401. Just one sample from the ship structure falls outside this, the pine plank, which could conceivably be a later addition. This plank is dating to after AD 1405.

The single piece of firewood from an oak that was probably felled in 1401-1402 avoided being used for heating or cooking, during the duration of the ship's usage, or it could have been used as dunnage.

The collection of barrel staves indicates diverse estimated felling dates from the last two decades of the 14th century, and the years around 1400. One barrel stave that might have bark edge preserved was probably felled in 1406-1407, allowing us clear evidence that the ship was in use for at least five years, as also indicated by the hypothesised addition of two pine wash strakes¹.

In terms of the provenance of the timbers, the analysis demonstrates diverse sources for the timbers for the building of this so-called ‘cog’ (or ‘Bremen Type’) ship. Both frames and hull planks are made from oaks that grew in the Low countries, strongly indicating that the ship was built in this region. Frames and planking from the region around the mouth of the Vistula River were undoubtedly transported to the Dutch shipbuilding site. We can state this with confidence, as there are numerous indications from dendrochronological analyses of other sites that the shipping of fine straight-grained oak boards and planks was a frequent phenomenon at this period (e.g. Daly 2007, 219-227, Daly et al 2021, Krapiec & Krapiec 2014, von Arbin et al 2022). The transport also of more bulky framing timbers from the region around the mouth of the Vistula River is a rarer phenomenon but this is the case for a contemporary ship to Svælget 2, found in The Netherlands – The so-called Ijsselcog has a mixture of timbers from the Baltic and from the Low Countries. While the majority of the Baltic timbers from the Ijsselcog are hull or ceiling planks, one rider is also of Baltic provenance (Domínguez-Delmás et al 2017, Waldus et al 2019).

The fact that all the dated barrel staves also show a Mouth of the Vistula provenance reinforces the picture that we have of this period, where barrels made from fine straight-grained boards (clapboards) found used as lining for wells and latrines in many urban sites throughout western Europe often are made of oaks from this same region (Daly 2007).

Methodology

Measuring of the samples and analysis of the tree-ring data is carried out using the program “DENDRO” (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the *t*-value (“*t*-test”) “CROS” (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. In the analysis, master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are used. For estimating the felling dating of the trees that the dated samples come from two sapwood statistics are used. For the oaks that are shown to be from the region around the mouth of the Vistula River, a sapwood average for northern Poland is used (c. 9-23 annual rings) (Wazny 1990). However, for the timbers that show a Low Countries provenance, it is more appropriate to use a sapwood average for Northern France (c. 4-34 rings) (Lambert 2006).

Literature

- von Arbin, S., Skowronek, T., Daly, A., Brorsson, T., Isaksson, S. & Seir, T., 2022. Tracing trade routes: examining the cargo of the 15th century Skaftö wreck. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 51.1. 112-144.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10572414.2022.2076518>
- Baillie, M.G.L. and Pilcher, J.R., 1973. A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bulletin* 33, 7-14.
- Bonde, N. and Jensen, J.S., 1995. The dating of a Hanseatic cog-ship in Denmark. What coins and tree rings can reveal in maritime archaeology. in Olsen, O., J.S. Madsen

¹ Mikkel H. Thomsen, pers. comm 08-05-2025.

- and F. Rieck (eds.), *Shipshape. Essays for Ole-Crumlin-Pedersen. On the occasion of his 60th anniversary February 24th 1995*, Roskilde, 103-121.
- Daly, A., 1998. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømmer fra Bindslev kirke, Hjørring Amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport nr. 18*, 1998, København.
- Daly, A., 2000. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømme fra Niels Hemmingsensgade, København, *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser report 2000:14*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2001. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømmer fra Boulevarden, Aalborg. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport 2001:7*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2007. *Timber, Trade and Tree-rings. A dendrochronological analysis of structural oak timber in Northern Europe, c. AD 1000 to c. AD 1650*. Ph.D. thesis submitted February 2007, University of Southern Denmark.
- Daly, A., 2011a. Dendro-geography – mapping the Northern European historic timber trade. P. Fraiture, 2011, *Tree Rings, Art, Archaeology, Brussels, coll. Scientia Artis* 7, 107-124.
- Daly, A., 2011b. Dendrochronological analysis of oak from a shipwreck, Skjernøysund 3, Mandal, Norway. *Chronology, Culture and Archaeology report 2*, University College Dublin, September 2011.
- Daly, A., 2015. Dateringsundersøgelse af tømmer fra Thomas B Thriges gade, Odense: dendro fase 1. *Dendro.dk rapport 2015:32*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A. 2019a. Ships and their timber source as indicators of connections between regions. *AmS-Skrifter* 27, 133–143, Stavanger, <https://doi.org/10.31265/ams-skrifter.v0i27.264>
- Daly, A., 2019b. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Peenemündung, Germany – Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. *Dendro.dk report 2019:42*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2020. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Femern, Denmark. *dendro.dk report 2020:44*, Copenhagen
- Daly, A., 2022. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from excavations in Aalborg, ÅHM6907 Algade mm, Denmark. *dendro.dk report 2022:44*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2023a. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from Oluf I Jensens gård, Køge. KNV01093-01. *dendro.dk report 2023:32*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2023b. Dendrochronological analysis of additional ship timbers from wreck Bi08 ‘Bispevika 8’, Oslo. *dendro.dk report 2023:75*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2025. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from two cogs, Varberg 3 and Varberg 4, Sweden. *dendro.dk report 2025:19*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., Jouttijärvi, A., Sass Jensen, L.M., Nicolajsen, T. & Ravn, M., 2021. The Vordingborg Boat: Investigation, presentation and interpretation of a 14th-century boat-find from Vordingborg Castle, Denmark. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 50.1, 97-115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572414.2021.1943406>
- Daly A. & Nymoen P., 2008. The Bøle Ship, Skien, Norway – Research history, dendrochronology and provenance, *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 37.1, p. 153–170.
- Daly, A. & Tyers, I., 2022. The sources of Baltic oak. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 139, 105550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2022.105550>.
- Domínguez-Delmás, M., Vorst, Y. & Vázquez Ruiz de Ocenda R., A., 2017. Dendrochronological research of samples from the Kampen cog shipwreck (The Netherlands). *Universidad de Santiago de Compostela Report nr: 2017001*, Lugo.
- Eriksen, O.H., 1992. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af skibsvrag fra Lille Kregme, Frederiksborg amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport 1992: 31*, 1 edn. Copenhagen.
- Eriksen, O.H., 2001. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømmer fra skibsvrag fundet på Dokøen, København. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport 2001:23*, Copenhagen.
- Hollstein, E. 1980. *Mitteleuropäische Eichenchronologie*. Trierer Grabungen und Forschungen 11. Mainz am Rhein.
- Jansma, E., 1995. *RememberRINGS. The Development and Application of Local and Regional Tree-Ring Chronologies of Oak for the Purposes of Archaeological and*

- Historical Research in the Netherlands*, dissertatie UvA (Nederlandse Archeologische Rapporten, 19).
- Krapiec M, Krapiec P. 2014. Dendrochronological analyses of the structural timbers and cargo of the copper ship. In: W Ossowski (ed.), *The Copper Ship. A Medieval ship and its cargo*: 143–160. National Maritime Museum, Gdańsk.
- Lambert, G.N., 2006. *Dendrochronologie, histoire et archéologie, modélisation du temps. Le logiciel Dendron II et le projet Historic Oaks*. Thèse de doctorat, 2006, Habilitation à Diriger les Recherches, Université de Franche-Comté. 2vol.
- Tyers, I.G., 1997. Dendro for Windows Program Guide, *ARCUS Report 340*, Sheffield.
- Waldus, W.B., Verweij, J.F., van der Velde, H.M., van Holk, A.F.L. & Vos S.E., 2019. The Ijsselcog project: from excavation to 3D reconstruction. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 48:2, 466-94. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1095-9270.12373>
- Wazny, T., 1990. *Aufbau und Anwendung der Dendrochronologie für Eichenholz in Polen*. PhD Thesis. Universität Hamburg, pp. 213.
- Worthington, M. & Miles, D. 2006. New College, Oxford. Tree-Ring Dating of the Bell Tower and Cloister Door. *Research Department Report Series 56*. English Heritage, 20 p.
- Zielski, A., 1997. *Uwarunkowania środowiskowe przyrostów radialnych sosny zwyczajnej (Pinus sylvestris L.) w Polsce północnej na podstawie wielowiekowej chronologii*, Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika. Toruń.
- Zielski, A. & Kamiński, P. 2003. Możliwości wykorzystania metody dendrochronologicznej do rekonstrukcji klimatu w średniowieczu (Possibilities of application of dendrochronological method for the climate reconstruction during the Medieval Period). In: K. Krążyński (Editor), *Pogranicze polsko-pruskie i krzyżackie*. Włocławek-Brodnica, p. 9-25.

Catalogue Ship timbers

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end		Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z311001a x16	Lynetteholm VIR2965 x1684 fra x1693 frame element	101	AD1219	AD1319	G	0	N	Q	H1	QUSP	1.34	after AD1329
Z3110029 x00	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1609 fra x0060 plank garboard carvel	92	AD1263	AD1354	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.87	after AD1359
Z3110039 x02	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1595 fra x296 plank hull clinker	141	AD1254	AD1394	G	7	N	T	S1	QUSP	2.09	AD1396-1410
Z3110049 x02	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1605 fra x0299 plank/wash strake clinker	66	AD1339	AD1404	G	29	N	T	S1	PISY	2.06	after AD1405
Z3110059	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x0261 x1638 plank hull clinker	76			G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.97	undated
Z3110069	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x270 x1650 rubbing strake	37			C	13	W	S	N	QUSP	2.82	undated
Z311007a	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x0057 x1654 keel	65			C	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	2.61	undated
Z3110089 x49	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x491 x1686 hull plank clinker	93	AD1256	AD1348	F	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.8	after AD1353
Z3110099 x18	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1704 x180 frame futtock	171	AD1215	AD1385	G	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	0.74	after AD1395
Z3110109 x67	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1705 x67 frame futtock	57	AD1345	AD1401	C	15	N	O	S1	QUSP	1.63	AD1402-20
Z3110119	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1703 x73 frame futtock	52			C	16	W	O	N	QUSP	1.61	undated
Z311012a	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1702 x79 frame futtock	42			C	13	N	O	S1	QUSP	3.06	undated
Z3110159 x20	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1737 x203 plank fragment (forecastle?)	271	AD1125	AD1395	G	11	N	R	S1	QUSP	0.86	AD1396-1407
Z311016a x40	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1715 x407 plank almost radial forecandle	169	AD1204	AD1372	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.19	after AD1382
Z311017a x20	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1716 x209 plank forecandle	293	AD1100	AD1392	G	14	N	R	S1	QUSP	0.87	AD1393-1401
Z3110189	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1717 x370 plank (deck?)	57			G	10	N	T	S1	PISY	2.76	undated
Z311019a	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1720 x22 large plank ceiling	42			G	0	N	T	N	QUSP	6.58	undated
Z311020a	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1718 x65 large plank edge tangential ceiling	55			G	20	N	T	S1	QUSP	2.24	undated
Z3110219 x35	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1734 x354 frame futtock	91	AD1308	AD1398	V	18	N	H	S1	QUSP	1.51	AD1399-1414
Z3110229	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1726 x20 frame futtock	73			C	13	N	H	S1	QUSP	1.94	undated
Z3110239	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1713 x21 frame futtock	61			C	11	N	S	S1	QUSP	2.08	undated
Z311024a x36	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1711 x367 frame beam in pres. forecandle	138	AD1262	AD1399	G	15	N	O	S1	QUSP	0.98	AD1400-7
Z3110259	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1728 x1446 little frame futtock fragment	104			G	0	N	Q	H1	QUSP	0.9	undated
Z3110279 x63	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1708 x63 keelson	68	AD1333	AD1400	G	12	?	Q	N	QUSP	3.52	AD1400-1401?
Z3110289 x29	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1744 x293 plank pres. sterncandle	291	AD1106	AD1396	G	9	N	R	N	QUSP	0.89	AD1396-1410
Z311030a x62	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1746 x62 plank carvel 1st SB strake	64	AD1248	AD1311	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.48	after AD1359

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.

Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.

QUSP = *Quercus* sp., oak. PISY = *Pinus* sp., pine. PCAB = *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = *Abies* sp., fir.

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Catalogue Artefacts

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end		Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z311014a x11	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1101 barrel stave	120	AD1220	AD1339	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	0.77	after AD1349
Z3110269 x14	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1729 x1497 firewood	39	AD1363	AD1401	C	10	?	W	N	QUSP	1.81	AD1401-02?
Z311029a x13	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1759 x1368 large barrel stave	124	AD1283	AD1406	G	18	?	R	N	QUSP	1.35	AD1406-07?
Z311031a x12	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1749 x1233 barrel stave	174	AD1223	AD1396	G	11	N	R	S1	QUSP	0.82	AD1397-1408
Z311032a x86	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1750 x864 barrel stave	186	AD1193	AD1378	G	7	N	R	S1	QUSP	0.8	AD1380-94
Z311033a x42	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1751 x427 barrel stave	131	AD1251	AD1381	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.8	after AD1391
Z311034a x10	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1752 x1087 barrel stave	141	AD1238	AD1378	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	0.83	after AD1388
Z311035a x13	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1753 x1328 barrel stave	102	AD1281	AD1382	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.92	after AD1392
Z311036a x10	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1754 x1045 barrel stave	160	AD1208	AD1367	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.66	after AD1377
Z3110379	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1755 x846 barrel stave	71			G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.57	undated
Z311038a x10	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1756 x1045 barrel stave	146	AD1249	AD1394	G	22	N	R	N	QUSP	0.78	AD1394-5
Z311039a x32	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1757 x328 barrel stave	114	AD1284	AD1397	G	15	N	R	S1	QUSP	1.18	AD1398-1405
Z311040a x20	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1758 x204 barrel stave	107	AD1273	AD1379	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.08	after AD1389
Z311041a x61	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1760 x619 barrel stave	143	AD1231	AD1373	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	0.98	after AD1383
Z311042a x75	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1761 x750 barrel stave	121	AD1264	AD1384	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.93	after AD1394
Z311043a x10	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1762 x1043 barrel stave	141	AD1247	AD1387	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.93	after AD1397
Z311044a x10	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1763 x1095 barrel stave	103	AD1284	AD1386	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.07	after AD1396

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.
 QUSP = *Quercus* sp., oak. PISY = *Pinus* sp., pine. PCAB = *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = *Abies* sp., fir.

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Not analysed dendrochronologically

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end		Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x1685 ceiling	15						T		QUSP.		
	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x282 curved timber							O		<i>Betula</i> sp.		

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.
 QUSP = *Quercus* sp., oak. PISY = *Pinus* sp., pine. PCAB = *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = *Abies* sp., fir.

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Averages

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end		Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Same tree												
Z3110 2 30 st	Svælget 2 VIR2965 x60 x62 same tree	107	AD1248	AD1354	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.11	after AD1370
Averages												
Z311M001 PL	Svælget 2 PL ship 8 timbers	300	AD1100	AD1399						QUSP	1.05	average
Z311M002 NL	Svælget 2 NL group 5 timbers	154	AD1248	AD1401						QUSP	2.37	average
Z311M003 PL	Svælget 2 PL staves 15 timbers	214	AD1193	AD1406						QUSP	0.91	average

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.
 QUSP = *Quercus* sp., oak. PISY = *Pinus* sp., pine. PCAB = *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = *Abies* sp., fir.

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